

STUDY OF KAMIL DEVANI CREATION**Meyliyeva Farangiz Uktam kizi**TSUULL faculty of philology 4th yearmeyliyevafarangiz04@gmail.com

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Abstract Kamil Devani, the son of Ismail Muhrkan, one of the creators who has his place and position in Khiva's literary environment, lived and created. Information about the life and activities of Kamil Devani can be found in “Tazkirai shuaro” of Hasanmurad Laffasi, “poets of Khorezm and musicians of Khorezm” by Babajon Tarroh, “Majmuat ush-shuaroyi payravi Feruzshahi” by Ahmad Tabibi.

The article talks about the study of the perfect devotional work, who conducted research in this regard.

Keywords: divan, second Navai, ghazal, mukhammas, secretary, poet.

The literature of the 19th and 20th centuries became the literature of the period of renewal. During this period, changes occurred in literature, art, music, and cultural life. This is also related to the name of the king and poet Muhammad Rahim Khan Feruz II. During the reign of Muhammad Rahim Khan Feruz II, various literary evenings were held in the palace, mushairas were organized, and this literary atmosphere created a foundation for the development of literature and art. During this period, various historical works and many poems were written. The creation of mukhammas and tatabbu came into existence. Under the leadership of Feruz, music, translation, and printing were established, reading flourished, and these activities became the basis for the formation of a beautiful environment. During the period of Feruz, Kamil Khorezmi, Ahmad Tabibi, Muhammad Yusuf Bayani, Mutrib Khonakharob, Chokar, Avaz O'tar Ogli, Muhammad Rahim Raghob, Kamil Devoni, Shinosi, Muznib and others created works. The environment of this period had a significant impact on the work of Kamil Devani, like many other poets.

Kamil Devani was a knowledgeable, capable, representative of this period who mastered several professions. Kamil Devani was born in the family of Ismail Muhrkan in the village called Sangar in the back of the city of Khiva. After the death of his father, he was brought up by his uncle Khudoybergan Muhrkan. Laffasiy says about this in his book: "...Devani was left behind by his father, and grew up under the guidance of his uncle Khudoybergan Muhrkan Devan, and received education from his uncle in literacy" (Laffasiy, 1992, 67- page). Kamil Devani studied at the Arab Khan madrasa in Khiva, studied Arabic, Persian languages, and the art of calligraphy. Yusufhaji Okhund (Doi) is his teacher. In addition, he has many skills. For example, he skillfully played dutor, tanbur, gizjak, and violin instruments. He made various knives, daggers, swords and put patterns on them. In addition, he wrote abiot and ta'rixs on marble stones and carved them easily into Islamic patterns. Kamil Devani created very effectively, there are 3 of his manuscripts of devan, which are currently stored in the main fund of the National Archives of the Republic of Uzbekistan under inventory numbers 901, 906, 1142. The poet copied the handwritten copy from these divans, which is kept under inventory number 1142. From this we can know that the poet's calligraphy skills were also very high. The poet lived fifty years and died in 1938.

The study of Kamil Devoni's work began during his lifetime. Information about the poet's life, work, and work was included in his contemporary Laffasi's "Tazkirai Shuaro", Khadim's "Khorazm Poets and Musicians", and Tabibi's "Majmuat ush-shuaroyi Payravi Feruzshahi". In his work, Bobojon Tarroh describes the poet as follows: "...he was of medium height, with a chubby face, big eyes and a big nose, and he used to play with his nose when he spoke. He was a bearded man. He was a dark-skinned man..." (Bobojon Tarroh – Xodim, 2011, p. 132).

Laffasiy in his book "Biographies of poets and writers of Khiva" enumerates a number of qualities of Devani, and also praises his secretarial work.

Devani had a high position not only in the field of secretarial work, but also in the field of poetry. The poet's poems have a playful tone, deep meaning, and

patriotism. Bobojon Tarroh in the 1994 edition of "Khorazm Poets and Musicians" notes that the poet has five different sciences. Appreciating the poet's work, he describes him as the Second Navoi: "...he was a good poet. It could be called the second Navoi" (Bobojon Tarroh-Xodim, 1994, p. 69). Of course, not everyone was given such a definition during this period.

Devani started to write poetry at the age of eighteen. Kamil gives himself the pseudonym Devani, and this name pleases the khan. Bobojon Tarroh wrote in his work: "... This pseudonym was given by Kamiljon himself and Muhammad Rahim Second accepted it when he wrote it down in his first poem. If Muhammad Rahim Secon did not like this pseudonym, he would given a pseudonym to the poet himself. Because of this, Kamiljon's literary pseudonym became Devani because he adopted his common name Muhammad Rahim Second..." (Bobojon Tarroh, Xorazm shoir va navozandalari, 2011, p. 130).

The fact that Devani's ghazals and muhammas are included in the Tabibi "Majmuat ush-shuaroi payravi Feruzshahi" and "Majmuai mukhammasoti ash-shuarai payravi Feruzshahi" is proof that despite being young, Devani had a decent position in his time.

In 1968, the "Uzbek Literature" Chrestomathy, Volume 2, contains information and examples of poets such as Kamil Devani, Hakima, Mutriba, Siddiqi, Chokar, Mutrib, Khonakharob, and Faqiri. This book contains 23 ghazals of Devoni, 1 mukhammas, 1 mukhammas to Ogahi's ghazal, and 1 musaddas. F. Musamammedova prepared samples from Devani's works for publication (O'zbek adabiyoti, 1968, p. 191-228).

Yusuf Rozimatov also conducted his research in the study of Kamil Devani's work. He published articles entitled "Kamil Devani" in the December 4, 1965 issue of "The true of Khorazm" newspaper, and "Singer of happiness" in the September 30, 1967 issue. Y.Rozimatov continued his work in this regard and in 1969 published the article "Komil Devani" in the magazine "Eastern Star". And finally, in 1971, he published a book called "Kamil Devani" consisting of the poet's poems. Yusuf

Rozimatov's book contains information about the poet's activities in social life, his work, and his relationship with poets. There are 50 ghazals, 1 mukhammas, 3 Navoi, 2 Munis and 2 Ogahi ghazals with mukhammas (Kamil Devoniy, She'rlar, Toshkent, 1971, p. 78).

Poet, dramatist Kamil Avaz published the book "Kamil Devani" in 2006. In this book, information about the poet's life and work is given in full, and in his book, he has attached 93 ghazals included in the Tabibi's book. In addition, in 2006, Sayyora Matkurbanova, a student of Urganch State University, defended her master's thesis on the work of Kamil Devoni on the topic "Historical Period and Creative Development". In 2022, Anvar Matniyazov published the book "Kamil Devani: Selected Works". This publication also contains 93 poems of the poet included in the Tabibi's books (Anvar Matniyazov, Komil Devoniy, Tanlangan asarlar, 2022, 185).

When studying the work of each creator, it is appropriate to study it first from the point of view of textual studies and source studies. The reason is that many mistakes are made in applying the language features of poets' works or their works. This is caused by the fact that the work of each creator is not realized on the basis of textual science.

Researches on Devani's work were carried out before and after independence, although few. However, the work of Kamil Devani has not yet been fully studied in the aspect of textual studies and source studies, and his ghazals in his divans and bayazs have not been fully published. This makes it necessary to carry out a lot of work on the study of the poet's work, prepare the poems of the poet for publication and make them available to the general public.

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